

DAMAGE INITIATION AND DEVELOPMENT IN CHOPPED STRAND MAT COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The mechanisms of damage initiation and development in a number of chopped strand mat composites have been studied. Damage has been characterised by undertaking cyclic tension tests in which the load is increased progressively until failure occurs. By measuring the reduction in Young's modulus the damage initiation strain as well as the rate of subsequent damage development have been determined for these materials. It has been shown that damage development depends strongly upon the properties of the matrix material as well as the fibre weight fraction. It has also been shown that surface modification of the fibres by silane treatment does not have any appreciable affect on damage development in these materials. The technique is also used to evaluate the process of damage development during long-term fatigue loading. It is believed that this simple test provides a useful method for characterising damage and ranking the behaviour of chopped strand mat composites taking into account resin matrix properties.

Keywords: CSM composites, damage initiation, modulus reduction, acoustic emission

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites are finding increasing use in a wide range of engineering components ranging from acid-resistant storage tanks for the chemical industry to primary load-bearing structures in the aerospace sector. In the case of high performance composites, the influence of varying the properties of the fibres and matrix have been examined in detail and are now quite well understood. This is not the case, however, for the mass market composites such as chopped strand mat laminates where the influence of varying the properties of the individual constituents on both short and long-term behaviour remains poorly understood. As a result of this somewhat limited understanding, codes and criteria for designing engineering components based on, for example, chopped-strand mat (CSM) composites are extremely conservative and, as a consequence, the full potential of these materials is not always achieved. A typical maximum design strain value of 0.2% is commonly adopted, although actual values in practice are usually less than this.

Yrieix *et al* (1) developed and applied a load cycling test to characterize damage initiation and development in polyester resin- and vinylester resin-based glass fibre composite specimens. This technique has been further developed by the present authors in order to better understand and assess the influence of varying parameters such as specimen geometry, strain rate and test temperature on the failure process in an epoxy vinyl ester resin based CSM composite (2). In the present paper, the load cycling test is used to examine the influence of varying fundamental material characteristics such as fibre type, matrix properties and fibre-matrix adhesion on the mechanisms of damage development in a number of CSM composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The majority of tests conducted in this study were undertaken on DERAKANE* 411-45 epoxy vinyl ester resin-based chopped strand mat composites. Laminates of nominal thickness two millimetres were manufactured by stacking (usually three) 300g/m² E-glass chopped strand mats, impregnating by hand rolling and compressing between two steel plates. All of the laminates were moulded at room temperature, and then subsequently post-cured for five hours at 100°C. The nominal fibre weight fraction in each case was approximately thirty percent. The influence of matrix properties on damage development was investigated by conducting a further series of tests on similar CSM composites based on an epoxy Novalac based vinyl ester with a high glass transition temperature (DERAKANE 470-30 resin) and high toughness rubber-modified epoxy based vinyl ester (DERAKANE 8084 resin).

Tests were undertaken on rectangular specimens having dimensions 150x10x2mm. The edges of the specimens were polished in order to remove any defects incurred during the cutting process. Initially, monotonic tensile tests were conducted to determine the Young's modulus, failure stress and failure strain of the composites. Following this, damage initiation and development in the materials was evaluated by conducting cyclic tensile tests in which the maximum load was increased systematically until failure occurred. In each case the specimens were first loaded to twenty-five percent of their expected failure stress and then unloaded. The maximum stress in subsequent load-cycles was then increased by constant increments until failure occurred. Typically, twelve load-unload cycles were undertaken on each specimen. The variation of strain during the test was measured over a 50mm section using a mechanical extensometer with a precision of five microns. Loading and unloading was undertaken at a crosshead speed of 5mm/minute.

Damage development during the test was quantified in a number of ways. Firstly, the reduction in Young's modulus during the test was used to define a damage parameter 'D' similar to that used by Yrieix *et al* (1). Here the damage in the n'th cycle 'D_n' is related to the corresponding modulus 'E_n' and the initial modulus E₀' by the relationship:

$$D_n = 1 - E_n/E_0$$

This damage parameter was then correlated with the maximum strain in the preceding cycle. Further information was obtained by recording the number of acoustic emission events exceeding 50dB.

A limited number of tests have also been undertaken in order to investigate the mechanisms of damage development during fatigue loading. Here, tests were undertaken on specimens with dimensions 150x10x2mm using a sinusoidal waveform at a frequency of 20Hz and a fatigue ratio 'R' of 0.1.

Finally, damage development was assessed by measuring the reduction in the intensity of transmitted light during the test. Here, a Canon Ci 20PM camera was placed approximately one metre in front of the specimen and a white light source directly behind it. The resulting images were analysed by computer using the Optilab (Graftek) image analysis system.

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3. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Monotonic tensile tests on the DERAKANE 411-45 resin based composites resulted in average values for the ultimate tensile strength, strain and initial modulus of 106 MPa, 1.64% and 7.1 GPa respectively. The stress-strain curves were initially linear but became progressively non-linear with increasing stress. A closer examination of the specimens during the test indicated that the onset of non-linearity coincided with the beginning of visual damage within the volume of the material. The onset and subsequent development of damage were then examined in more detail by load-cycling the specimens and determining a damage parameter based on the reduction of Young's modulus as outlined above. Figure 1 shows a typical damage development graph for this material. The damage threshold strain, ϵ_d , was then determined by extrapolating the data back to a zero value of damage 'D' as shown by the solid line in Figure 1. The resulting value of ϵ_d for this particular test is 0.49%, a typical value for this material. The slope of the damage-strain graph also yields information concerning the rate of damage development with increasing applied strain. For the test presented in Fig. 1 the damage development rate is 10.6 %/%, a typical value for this material at room temperature. The failure process was studied in more detail by stopping certain tests before fracture, then sectioning and polishing before examination under either an optical or scanning electron microscope. It was found that initial damage took the form of fibre-matrix debonding around fibres oriented perpendicular to the applied load, and particularly with fibres lying between 45° and 90° to the applied stress. With continued loading, debonding became extensive within the volume of the material resulting in a significant increase in the opacity of the specimen as could be determined via the transmitted light apparatus. Just prior to failure, large matrix cracks appeared at several locations along the surface of the specimens.

The load cycling test was then used to examine the influence of varying the properties of the material constituents on damage initiation in these chopped strand mat composites. The following sections consider the influence of the fibre type, fibre weight fraction, fibre-matrix interfacial strength and matrix properties on damage initiation and development.

3.1 Fibre

Composite laminates based on the DERAKANE 411-45 resin were produced with two types of reinforcing fibres, these being 300g/m² powder bonded E-glass CSM and an acid resistant glass; (M113 E-glass CSM from Vetrotex SA, France and M-751 ECRGLAS (TM) CSM from Owens Corning Fiberglass, respectively). Load-cycling indicated that the damage threshold strain was the same for both materials (approximately 0.5%). It was interesting to note, however, that the rate of damage development in the ECRGLAS composite was only one half of that in the E-glass laminate. The precise reasons for this significant difference in mechanical behaviour are not known. Both fibres have almost identical moduli, physical dimensions and strength. The chemical nature of the fibre surface treatment is, however, unknown and may have an influence on the strength of the fibre:matrix interface.

3.2 Fibre Weight Fraction

The influence of the fibre weight fraction, W_f , was assessed by reducing the weight of resin applied to the three 300g/m² glass mats. Three fibre weight fractions were considered, these being nominally 15, 30 and 60%. The resulting damage curves are presented in Figure 2 where it is clear that the damage threshold decreases with increasing W_f . The average values of damage initiation strain for the 60, 30 and 15 wt% laminates were 0.41, 0.49 and 0.65% respectively. It is believed that the higher damage threshold in the low weight fraction composites is at least in part due to the superior impregnation of the fibre bundles. Increasing W_f also has the effect of increasing the initial rate of damage development as well as the ultimate failure strain.

3.3 Fibre Surface Treatment

In a preceding section it was noted that initial failure in these CSM composites took the form of debonding at the interface of fibres aligned at approximately ninety degrees to the applied stress. Here, an attempt was made to increase the degree of fibre-matrix adhesion, and therefore the damage threshold, by adding 0.5% by weight of a methacrylate functional tri-methoxy silane coupling agent to the resin, prior to the impregnation of the reinforcement (A174 from Union Carbide Corporation). Rather surprisingly, it was found that the addition of the silane coupling agent had no significant effect neither on the damage threshold strain nor the rate of damage development, Figure 3. A detailed fractographical study of the failed samples is required in order to ascertain if the amount of residual matrix was greater on the treated fibres.

3.4 Matrix Properties

The influence of varying the properties of the matrix on the processes of damage initiation and development in these materials was examined by conducting a further series of tests on CSM laminates based on a high temperature resistant epoxy Novalac based vinyl ester, DERAKANE 470-30 resin ($K_{Ic}=0.61 \text{ MPa.m}^{1/2}$) and a high toughness, rubber-modified epoxy-based vinyl ester, DERAKANE 8084 ($K_{Ic}=1.18 \text{ MPa.m}^{1/2}$). The values were then compared with the previously determined data for the DERAKANE 411-45 resin ($K_{Ic}=0.81 \text{ MPa.m}^{1/2}$). The results of these tests are summarised in Figure 4. From the figure it is clear that the matrix plays a significant role in determining both the strain at which the onset of damage occurs as well as the subsequent rate of damage development. The extremely tough DERAKANE 8084 resin based composite exhibits the highest damage threshold as well as the lowest rate of damage development. The average values of ϵ_d for the DERAKANE 470-30, 411-45 and 8084 resin based composite systems were 0.32, 0.49 and 0.75% respectively, values which are in some cases considerably higher than the currently accepted maximum design strain values of 0.2%.

An examination of the specimens after fracture indicated that damage in the DERAKANE 8084 and 411-45 resin based CSM laminates took the form of debonding within the fibre bundles lying at 90° to the axis of applied stress, as opposed to the more extensive debonding and matrix cracking in the more rigid and higher T_g DERAKANE 470-30 resin based laminate.

4. DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT DURING FATIGUE LOADING

The process of damage development during continuous dynamic loading was assessed by undertaking a series of fatigue tests at 20Hz and $R=0.1$. The tests were interrupted at regular intervals and the modulus measured before re-loading to the same applied stress level. Damage development curves corresponding to specimens loaded to a maximum stress of 48 and 60MPa (approximately equivalent to 45 and 57% of the ultimate tensile strength respectively) are presented in Figure 5. In both cases, damage relating to the initial applied strain is introduced during the first load excursion. Subsequently, damage development in the more highly loaded specimen is rapid, taking the form of extensive debonding between the fibres oriented at angles between 45° and 90° to the loading direction. In the specimen loaded to a maximum stress of 48MPa, the damage, (taking the form of debonding between fibres at 90°) increased initially and then remained constant for a prolonged period of time. After extended cycling, matrix cracks perpendicular to the loading direction began to appear on the surface of the specimen resulting in an acceleration of the measured damage and then ultimate failure. The technique has also been applied successfully to assess damage development during long-term creep loading.

5. OTHER TECHNIQUES FOR QUANTIFYING DAMAGE

In an earlier section, it was reported that damage in these composites resulted in a significant increase in opacity and therefore a reduction in the level of transmitted light. In an attempt to quantify the level of damage, the variation in the intensity of transmitted light was measured using a conventional CCD camera and video system. A typical light intensity curve for the DERAKANE 411-45 resin composite is presented along with the corresponding acoustic emission data in Figure 6. From the graph it is clear that both the acoustic emission and light intensity curves exhibit the same general shape. It is important to note, however, that the optical technique is somewhat less successful in detecting initial damage at low strain levels. This is hardly surprising since the light intensity measurements are taken over a 50x10mm section and initial debonds are measured in terms of microns. Light intensity measurements were made on the three composite materials presented in the previous section.

6. CONCLUSIONS

A number of test techniques have been evaluated to study damage development in chopped strand mat composites based on DERAKANE epoxy vinyl ester resins. Load-cycling under increasing applied stress has been shown to be a particularly useful technique since it enables the damage threshold strain as well as the subsequent rate of damage development to be studied. The technique can also be applied in order to study the processes of energy absorption during failure. The test is therefore of value for the determination of realistic mechanical performance data for design purposes and for material comparisons and selection. The damage initiation strain was found to be dependent on the fibre weight fraction varying from 0.41 to 0.68% for 60 to 15 weight percent respectively. The typical industrial practice value of 30wt% of fibres showed a damage initiation strain of 0.49%. The damage initiation strain was found to be highly dependent on the matrix resin characteristics, giving 0.32% for the rigid, high Tg DERAKANE 470-30 resin; 0.49% for the standard epoxy based DERAKANE 411-45 resin and 0.75% for the rubber modified epoxy based DERAKANE 8084 resin. All values were in excess of the current maximum design strain value of 0.2%.

The data suggest that the high toughness rubber modified epoxy based DERAKANE 8084 resin would be particularly suitable for very highly stressed applications involving dynamic loading, such as high performance marine craft.

Finally, damage progression in these materials has also been successfully evaluated by monitoring the increase in acoustic activity as well as the reduction in the intensity of transmitted light.

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References

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Figure 1. Typical damage development curve for the DERAKANE 411-45 epoxy vinyl ester resin/ E-glass CSM composite.

Figure 2. The influence of fibre weight fraction on damage development curves for the DERAKANE 411-45 epoxy vinyl ester resin E-glass CSM composites.

Figure 3. The addition of Union Carbide A-174 Silane coupling agent to the DERAKANE 411-45 epoxy vinyl ester resin and its effect on the damage development of the E-glass CSM composite.

Figure 4. The influence of matrix resin type on the damage development processes of E-glass CSM composites (nominally 900 g/m² glass).

Figure 5. Damage development during room temperature fatigue loading at 20Hz and R=0.1 in the epoxy based vinyl ester resin DERAKANE 411-45 CSM composite.

Figure 6. A comparison of Acoustic Emission events (>50dB) and variation in transmitted light intensity during the damage development process of the DERAKANE 411-45 epoxy vinyl ester resin / E-glass CSM composite.